

**A NOTE ON FINITE SUMS OF PRODUCTS OF BERNSTEIN
BASIS POLYNOMIALS AND HYPERGEOMETRIC POLYNOMIALS**

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Received: 6/12/17, Revised: 11/30/17, Accepted: 3/21/18, Published: 3/30/18

Abstract

This note considers finite sums of products of Bernstein basis polynomials and Gauss hypergeometric polynomials for which all three parameters are non-positive integers. A simple formula is derived for such sums and an interesting binomial identity is obtained as a special case.

1. Preliminaries

The k th Bernstein basis polynomial of degree $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is defined by

$$B_{k,n}(z) = \binom{n}{k} z^k (1-z)^{n-k}, \quad z \in \mathbb{C}.$$

The set $\{B_{k,n}(z)\}_{k=0}^n$ is a basis for the space of polynomials of degree at most n with complex coefficients. Since

$$\sum_{k=0}^n B_{k,n}(z) = (z + (1-z))^n = 1,$$

the Bernstein basis polynomials of degree n form a partition of unity.

For $p, q \in \mathbb{N}$, the *generalized hypergeometric function* is defined by

$${}_pF_q(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_p; \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_q; z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\alpha_1)_n \cdots (\alpha_p)_n}{(\gamma_1)_n \cdots (\gamma_q)_n} \frac{z^n}{n!}, \quad z \in \mathbb{C} \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_p, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_q \in \mathbb{C}$ and $(\rho)_n$ is the Pochhammer symbol defined by

$$(\rho)_n = \begin{cases} 1 & n = 0 \\ \rho(\rho+1) \cdots (\rho+n-1) & n > 0. \end{cases}$$

The ${}_2F_1$ case is called the Gauss hypergeometric function

$${}_2F_1(\alpha, \beta; \gamma; z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\alpha)_n (\beta)_n}{(\gamma)_n} \frac{z^n}{n!}, \quad z \in \mathbb{C}. \quad (2)$$

Clearly ${}_2F_1$ is symmetric in α and β .

The series in (2) terminates if and only if either $-\alpha \in \mathbb{N}$ or $-\beta \in \mathbb{N}$. In this case, the series is called a hypergeometric polynomial. If $-\alpha \in \mathbb{N}$, then for $m = -\alpha$,

$${}_2F_1(\alpha, \beta; \gamma; z) = \sum_{n=0}^m \binom{m}{n} (-1)^n \frac{(\beta)_n}{(\gamma)_n} z^n. \tag{3}$$

If $-\beta \in \mathbb{N}$, first use symmetry of ${}_2F_1$ in α and β , then apply (3). In general, if $-\gamma \in \mathbb{N}$, the series in (2) does not converge, except in the case that the series terminates and $-\gamma > m$. (See [2] for a definition of ${}_2F_1$ explicitly including the case of negative integer values of γ .)

We note that in the special case $\beta = \gamma$, the hypergeometric polynomial simplifies as

$${}_2F_1(\alpha, \beta; \gamma; z) = {}_1F_0(\alpha; z) = (1 - z)^{-\alpha}. \tag{4}$$

In the non-terminating case, Equation (4) only holds for $|z| < 1$, but in the polynomial case it is just a statement of the binomial theorem and thus holds for all $z \in \mathbb{C}$.

In this note, we prove some simple, but non-trivial results on sums of products of Bernstein basis polynomials and hypergeometric polynomials. More specifically, we will establish a formula for finite sums of the form

$$\sum_{k=0}^N B_{k,N}(z) {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -N; \varphi(z)),$$

for $m, N \in \mathbb{N}$.

We will use the contiguous relationship

$$\gamma {}_2F_1(\alpha, \beta; \gamma; z) - \alpha {}_2F_1(\alpha + 1, \beta; \gamma + 1; z) + (\alpha - \gamma) {}_2F_1(\alpha, \beta; \gamma + 1; z) = 0 \tag{5}$$

proved in [1]. Also see [4] for an up-to-date list of known contiguous relations for the Gauss hypergeometric function. Since (5) holds for all $z \in \mathbb{C}$, it also holds if we replace z with $\varphi(z)$ for any \mathbb{C} -valued function φ , or branch of φ if it is multi-valued.

2. Main Results

Theorem 1. *Let $N \in \mathbb{N}^+$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$ with $m \leq N$. For φ a \mathbb{C} -valued function (or a branch of a \mathbb{C} -valued function) and z in its domain, if*

$$S_m(n) = \sum_{k=0}^n B_{k,n}(z) {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -n; \varphi(z))$$

then $S_m(N) = S_m(m)$. Thus, if $N \in \mathbb{N}^+$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$ with $m \leq N$, the sum $S_m(N)$ depends only on m .

Proof. Note that $S_m(N) = S_m(m) + \sum_{n=m+1}^N S_m(n) - S_m(n-1)$. We prove that $\sum_{n=m+1}^N S_m(n) - S_m(n-1) = 0$.

For $n > m$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & S_m(n) - (1-z)S_m(n-1) \\
 = & \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} z^k (1-z)^{n-k} {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) \\
 & - (1-z) \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{k} z^k (1-z)^{n-1-k} {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -(n-1); \varphi(z)) \\
 = & \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} z^k (1-z)^{n-k} {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) \\
 & - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{k} z^k (1-z)^{n-k} {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -(n-1); \varphi(z)) \\
 = & (1-z)^n + z^n {}_2F_1(-n, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) \\
 & + \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \binom{n}{k} z^k (1-z)^{n-k} {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) \\
 & - (1-z)^n - \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{k} z^k (1-z)^{n-k} {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -(n-1); \varphi(z)) \\
 = & z^n {}_2F_1(-n, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) + \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} z^k (1-z)^{n-k} \left[\binom{n}{k} {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) \right. \\
 & \left. - \binom{n-1}{k} {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -(n-1); \varphi(z)) \right] \\
 = & z^n {}_2F_1(-n, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) \\
 & + \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} z^k (1-z)^{n-k} \left[\frac{n}{k} \binom{n-1}{k-1} {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) \right. \\
 & \left. - \frac{n-k}{k} \binom{n-1}{k-1} {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -(n-1); \varphi(z)) \right] \tag{6} \\
 = & z^n {}_2F_1(-n, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) \\
 & + \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{k-1} z^k (1-z)^{n-k} \left[\frac{1}{k} \left(n {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - (n-k) {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -(n-1); \varphi(z)) \right) \right] \\
 = & z^n {}_2F_1(-n, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) \\
 & + \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{k-1} z^k (1-z)^{n-k} \left[\frac{1}{k} \left(k {}_2F_1(-(k-1), -m; -(n-1); \varphi(z)) \right) \right] \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= z^n {}_2F_1(-n, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) \\
 &\quad + \sum_{k'=0}^{n-2} \binom{n-1}{k'} z^{k'+1} (1-z)^{n-k'-1} {}_2F_1(-k', -m; -(n-1); \varphi(z)) \quad (8) \\
 &= z^n {}_2F_1(-n, -m; -n; \varphi(z)) - z^n {}_2F_1(-(n-1), -m; -(n-1); \varphi(z)) \\
 &\quad + \sum_{k'=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{k'} z^{k'+1} (1-z)^{n-k'-1} {}_2F_1(-k', -m; -(n-1); \varphi(z)) \\
 &= z^n (1-z)^m - z^n (1-z)^m \\
 &\quad + z \sum_{k'=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{k'} z^{k'} (1-z)^{n-1-k'} {}_2F_1(-k', -m; -(n-1); \varphi(z)) \quad (9) \\
 &= z S_m(n-1),
 \end{aligned}$$

where (6) follows from the binomial coefficient identities

$$\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n}{k} \binom{n-1}{k-1} \quad \text{and} \quad \binom{n-1}{k} = \frac{n-k}{k} \binom{n-1}{k-1},$$

(7) uses the contiguous relationship in (5), (8) follows from the substitution $k' = k - 1$, and (9) follows from the symmetry of ${}_2F_1$ in α and β , and an application of (4).

This argument implies $S_m(n) = S_m(n - 1)$, and the result follows. □

Corollary 1. *Let $N \in \mathbb{N}^+$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$ with $m \leq N$. If φ is a \mathbb{C} -valued function (or a branch of a \mathbb{C} -valued function) and z is in its domain, then*

$$\sum_{k=0}^N B_{k,N}(z) {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -N; \varphi(z)) = (1 - z\varphi(z))^m. \quad (10)$$

Proof. The result follows from Theorem 1 and the binomial theorem:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{k=0}^N B_{k,N}(z) {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -N; \varphi(z)) &= \sum_{k=0}^m B_{k,m}(z) {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -m; \varphi(z)) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^m B_{k,m}(z) {}_1F_0(-k; \varphi(z)) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} z^k (1-z)^{m-k} (1-\varphi(z))^k \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} (z - z\varphi(z))^k (1-z)^{m-k} \\
 &= (1 - z\varphi(z))^m.
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Specific identities that are special cases of Corollary 1 include,

- (i) $\sum_{k=0}^N B_{k,N}(z) {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -N; z) = (1 - z^2)^m$; and in particular $\sum_{k=0}^N B_{k,N}(i) {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -N; i) = 2^m$,
- (ii) $\sum_{k=0}^N B_{k,N}(z) {}_2F_1(-k, -m; -N; 1 - z) = (z^2 - z + 1)^m$,
- (iii) $\sum_{k=0}^N B_{k,N}(z) {}_2F_1\left(-k, -m; -N; \frac{1}{z}\right) = \begin{cases} 1 & m = 0 \\ 0 & m > 0, \end{cases}$
- (iv) $\sum_{k=0}^N B_{k,N}(z) {}_2F_1\left(-k, -m; -N; 1 + \frac{1}{z}\right) = z^m$.

The following corollary establishes a binomial identity that is also an immediate consequence of Corollary 1.

Corollary 2. *Let $N \in \mathbb{N}^+$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$ with $m \leq N$. Then*

$$\sum_{k=0}^N B_{k,N}(x) {}_2F_1\left(-k, -m; -N; \frac{1+x-y}{x}\right) = (y-x)^m, \quad y \in \mathbb{C}, x \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}. \quad (11)$$

A remarkable aspect of this identity is the way that monomial terms of degree other than m in the summation in (11) combine and vanish, leaving only terms of degree m involved in the binomial expansion. For example, in the case with $m = 3$ and $N = 4$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^4 B_{k,4}(x) {}_2F_1\left(-k, -3; -4; \frac{1+x-y}{x}\right) \\ &= x^4 - 4x^3 + 6x^2 - 4x + 1 \\ &\quad - x^4 - 3x^3y + 6x^3 + 9x^2y - 12x^2 - 9xy + 10x + 3y - 3 \\ &\quad + 3x^3y + 3x^2y^2 - 3x^3 - 12x^2y - 6xy^2 + 9x^2 + 15xy + 3y^2 - 9x - 6y + 3 \\ &\quad - 3x^2y^2 - xy^3 + 6x^2y + 6xy^2 + y^3 - 3x^2 - 9xy - 3y^2 + 4x + 3y - 1 \\ &\quad + xy^3 - 3xy^2 + 3xy - x \\ &= y^3 - 3xy^2 + 3x^2y - x^3 \\ &= (y-x)^3. \end{aligned}$$

As another application, Corollary 1 can be used to derive the generating function for Krawtchouk polynomials. For $0 < p < 1$, $N \in \mathbb{N}$, and $x \in \mathbb{N}$ with $x \leq N$, the

Krawtchouk polynomials are defined for $\nu \in \mathbb{N}$ with $\nu \leq x$ by

$$K_\nu(x, p, N) = {}_2F_1\left(-\nu, -x; -N; \frac{1}{p}\right),$$

(see [3], for instance). In (10), let $z = \frac{t}{1+t}$ and $\varphi(z) = \frac{1}{p}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (1+t)^{-N} \sum_{\nu=0}^N \binom{N}{\nu} {}_2F_1\left(-\nu, -x; -N; \varphi\left(\frac{t}{1+t}\right)\right) t^\nu \\ = \sum_{n=0}^N B_{\nu, N}\left(\frac{t}{1+t}\right) {}_2F_1\left(-\nu, -x; -N; \varphi\left(\frac{t}{1+t}\right)\right) \\ = \left(1 - \left(\frac{t}{1+t}\right) \frac{1}{p}\right)^x = \left(1 - \left(\frac{1-p}{p}\right) t\right)^x (1+t)^{-x}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\sum_{\nu=0}^N \binom{N}{\nu} {}_2F_1\left(-\nu, -x; -N; \frac{1}{p}\right) t^\nu = \left(1 - \left(\frac{1-p}{p}\right) t\right)^x (1+t)^{N-x},$$

which is the generating function for Krawtchouk polynomials as given in [3]

Acknowledgement. I would like to thank the anonymous referee for several useful suggestions.

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